

EFFECT OF PAMAM LAYER ON THE INTERFACE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITES

Y. Li*, Q. Peng, X. He, R. Wang, L. Mei, C. Wang

Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China,

* Corresponding author (liyibin@hit.edu.cn)

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1. Introduction

The carbon fiber reinforced composites have been widely used due to their high stiffness, high strength, and low density[1]. Whereas, because the carbon fibers (CFs) have small active specific surface area and low surface energy, the cohesive force between CFs and the matrix is weak[2]. Therefore, the exploration of fiber/matrix interface has never been stopped.

Dendrimers, new nano-scale globular macromolecules[3], also known as cauliflower or starburst, are introduced to functionalize the CFs. The dendrimers can introduce an adsorption layer on the CFs. The dendritic structures of them provide hundreds of functional groups on the CF surface, which supply much more opportunity to react with matrix. Many amino groups at the periphery of PAMAM provide more active sites, which can react as a "bridge" to connect the matrix and oxidized CFs together[4,5]. On this basis, we further demonstrate the influence of dendrimers layer on load transfer at the fiber/matrix interface. The IFSS of composites reinforced by dendrimer layer is increased by as much as 74% in comparison with original composite. This method is expected to provide us an optimum condition for functionalized CFs with no complex processing condition, no toxic contamination and easy controllability.

2. Experimental

The dendrimer used is poly-(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimer (G 0) with ethylenediamine core and amino surface groups (Aldrich Incorp.). The functionalized CFs is prepared by immersing the pretreated substrates

Functional groups and morphology of the resulting materials are examined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Fourier transform-infrared spectrometer (FTIR), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Surface chemical analysis

XPS and FTIR measurements have been performed on different CF samples, as show in Fig.1 and Fig.2. The results show that the chemical interaction between PAMAM and CF occurred..

3.2 surface free energy

The fiber surface free energy obtained by double fluid method based on the contact angle is shown in Fig. 3.

3.3 Adhesion property between carbon fiber and epoxy matrix

The IFSS of the raw CF composite is 44 MPa. Whereas for PAMAM-treated CF composite, the IFSS is increased to 75 MPa, (74% increment compared to that of the as-received CF composite). This is due to the excellent wetting property of the dendrimers layer as well as the introduction of amino groups, which can interact with the epoxy resin as curing agent.

4. Conclusion

This study shows that the functionalization of the CF by use of the PAMAM dendrimer is an efficient technique for increasing interface strength as directly confirmed by XPS, FTIR and IFSS. The surface free energy is increased about 159% compared to the raw carbon fiber. Single fiber-microbond tensile test indicates that the IFSS of the PAMAM/CF composite is significantly increased by as much as 74% in comparison with that of the raw CF composite. The giant enhancement is mainly attributed to large amount of active sites, which react with matrix and form chemical link.

Fig.1 XPS wide scan spectra of the CF: a) bear fiber b) after an acid treatment, c) CFs after a reaction with dendrimer

Fig.2 FTIR spectra of the CF (a) CFs: a) after an acid treatment, b) CFs after a reaction with dendrimer

Fig.3 surface free energies of different CF samples

Fig.4 IFSS of the different PAMAM concentration by the single fiber microbond test

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